

Ethos of Open Science Breakout Session

August 11, 2022

TOPS Community Forum

Verbal Discussion and Chat Text

Anonymous Transcript

[Open Science Knowledge Platform](#) – course commissioned by the Dutch funding agency

[Open Life Science](#) has a great course which is very ethos focused - Sharing - Connecting – Empowering

[Turing Way](#) is brilliant!

I would love to learn more about neurodivergence in open science. Do you have information you could send? Or is it possible to be involved in a conversation about neurodivergence in open science?

[Guidance: Designing Learning for Autistic and Neurodiverse Students](#) | OpenTEL
[AutSPACES](#): GitHub repository curated by the autistic community, but it is mostly autism specific

Are you communicating with other big open science educators like the European open science cloud? And other big open science education repositories/organizations like FORRT?

Open Data Breakout Session

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Anonymous Transcript

NASA TOPS Moderator: Yvonne Ivey Parker

BEGINNING OF TRANSCRIPT

TOPS Moderator:

Alright, my name's Yvonne Ivey Parker. I am the TOPS (Transform to Open Science) program manager as well as the equity lead. I'm so excited to have everyone here to jump into open data. As you can see, I'm sharing my screen and we'll be going over some topics to really get everyone's thoughts around what open data means for an open science curriculum. I don't know if folks want to come off mute and introduce themselves. But we really want to make this interactive and so would anyone like to go first introducing themselves?

TOPS Moderator:

Anyone else want to jump in and introduce themselves? Otherwise, we'll get started discussing the prompt. No pressure. Let's talk about open data. As we shared in the intro slides, we really wanted to focus the open data module on the use of data repositories and I'm so happy to see so many folks who either work in data repositories or are interested in finding out better or more improved best practices that would facilitate FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) and open data.

By the end of the module that we're currently in the process of developing – our goal for our learners and users and contributors of the modules is to essentially make sure that the learners feel comfortable creating a data management plan that follows FAIR principles, including assigning a license, copyright, metadata tagging, and assigning PIDs (Personal Identifiable Information) – learners should feel comfortable utilizing and assigning metadata, citing data in their work. We structured this as an open discussion. I dropped in some topics that I found would be useful for this discussion.

And we have folks who are on the call. Let's begin chatting through this. I'll just start with the first question. Would anyone like to come off mute and describe key characteristics of open data from their perspective, whether it be from your experience as a researcher or user of NASA data? From your own personal experience, when you think of describing open data?

Speaker 2:

Perhaps I will describe a little bit of these elements that you listed in terms of my experience. About 15 years ago, I started to learn [about] how to share the data. And the main reason was the collaborations that they had with NASA and with NOAA and how all digital resources would be useful for other users. We're talking about data models and the code scripts, et cetera. One of the elements was not just to provide the data access, which is probably the keyword access to the data – [but make it] freely available and the well documented. One element is not just to create data but making it accessible and useful to the users. One of the key things we started 15 years ago with this was a rudimentary creation of metadata files, descriptions and exercises or examples on how to use the data and get access to that. So that was an interesting venue because it – at least for me – was a foundation on some beginning principles of FAIR and in how we should share the data and that problem. My two cents here.

TOPS Moderator:

Thank you. Would anyone else like to describe their experience or share their thoughts around key characteristics of open data?

Speaker 7:

We had an **Open Access mandate** that was just rolled out at the beginning of this year. And part of the Open Access publishing was also to promote open data and one of the [pieces of] feedback that we got from the researchers in the labs was that that they didn't have any kind of **training in how to draft a data management plan**, or how to keep data – they didn't have dedicated data managers. And [at] their universities, some of them had some people to help and others had nobody to help or advise them. I think one of the barriers is just trying to make this easier for people, given that this is – I think a lot of people don't need to be convinced that open data is good and that their hearts are in the right place. They want to be able to share it. But [for some people], this is yet another hurdle for them. And I think the research universities really need to step up to the plate. That's what I have the most experience with – academics need to step up and really start **training graduate students, postdocs, lab managers, technicians** – the people [that are] actually generating the data, right? It's not going to be the principal investigators of the lab. It's going to be the people actually generating the data. And so that needs to become a norm, I think, and it can't become a norm if there isn't [any] support for it and **training**. And rewards from academia as well.

TOPS Moderator:

Thank you for that. I think that is a great segway into my next slide where I really want to get folks talking around how we're envisioning our module to be developed, but more specifically, when we talk about open data in context of the

broader open core – it's ensuring that folks have support, folks have the training, and they have the infrastructure to be successful in this.

Over the past 18 months, as we've conducted a roadshow around transforming communities to lean into open science incentives that you brought up, as well as ensuring that folks have the support from their institutions – has also been a point of contention. But also, more specifically for a lot of folks, open data means something different depending on where you come from and as we were structuring this module around open data – which follows the first module, which is the “ethos of open science” – we wanted to make sure that folks have the support to really lean in and not only get familiar with the best practices around open science, but be able to understand and to ensure that we're able to collaborate and really push an open science design.

If you can still see my slide, I would really love folks' thoughts. You really have to lean in and set the tone for this. But in your experience, what do you find? What's important to cover in this lesson around open data?

[Speaker 4], go ahead.

Speaker 4:

I feel like one thing that I'm not seeing explicitly is data formatting because it's really important to share data, but just myself personally working with data, different data sets and having to deal with different formatting issues. Well, coding issues because the data formats are not necessarily universal. Is there any training that will be done to for this open data concept where there's a **universal data formatting structure** that will be taught to make it easier to deal with the data sets that will be in this repository?

TOPS Moderator:

That's a great question. I would like to point out that the open core is actually science-domain agnostic and so the focus of open core is not specifically to dive into a specific data format to conduct science. However, [the focus is] to discuss what the principles of open data are. Over the course of my being at NASA, which is a little over five years, every science domain and discipline has their own data formats, and it would be an obvious task to try to get folks who've been using specific data for their observations to all conform to one specific format.

Speaker 7:

One question I had – this is (Name) again – should that be something that the repositories themselves take on as a challenge and get the various subdisciplines together that use a particular repository and get them at least to **agree on a data format**? I wonder if there is anyone here from a repository and is that being discussed? I'd be interested to know. Thanks.

Speaker 5:

We deal with land processes and remote sensing data. And yes, there are conversations around data formats, and as a repository we can make **recommendations to those projects** highlighting the pros and cons of selecting format A over format B. But ultimately, we support what we get from those PIs (principal investigators) and so I think – at least in our domain – we're shifting to having more of a **cloud friendly format environment**. And we're making those arguments to them. It's kind of a relationship thing where we have to communicate back to them (the data providers) that putting it in this format will make it more interoperable, it'll make it more usable and we'll be able to plug it into those services that allow for discoverability. I don't know if it just lands on one group in this chain, right? I think there's a lot of communication that has to go back and forth across multiple levels.

Speaker 12:

National Microbiome Data Collaborative (NMDC) is focused on standardizing both the data and the metadata for things as well. We provide **metadata templates** that researchers doing microbiome data can use to **standardize all the metadata**. We're pretty rigorous about the metadata that we require so that the data is maximally FAIR, which I've also seen shared here – findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. We're huge on open data, data sharing – so anything for microbiome data that's kind of our bread and butter. And then all of the data that's in the NMDC has been **run through standardized bioinformatic workflows**. So, the actual results are comparable across. That helps to standardize the actual data that's in there. In terms of the process data...we do have **resources and trainings** for people to work with the metadata standards as well as the data portal and the bioinformatic workflows. Anyone [who] wants to chat more about that? I'm happy to chat. We love doing joint trainings and chatting about anything too. It's exciting to see this discussion happening.

Speaker 10:

I'll just add to that since I work at a repository as well. We're very similar to a NMDC but smaller. But we also have standards for our repositories so I understand that this is supposed to be much more open and agnostic to a domain, but I do think it is important that you...when talking about making your data open or sharing your data. That part of the lessons could be about looking into that community where you're going to submit your data before you start organizing your data. I would say a lot of communities have built templates and standards and metadata standards and data formats. I think that is an important place for students to start. Whoever is going to be generating this data so that they don't have to reformat at the end. And I think that's a really, really difficult process and thinking about doing that at the very beginning. So even if it's not specific like the court, the court doesn't have to be specific to a domain, but it can actually drive people to. Start somewhere and I think it would be where there were data is going to go and actually start formatting it towards that data

repositories' or that community requirements and – at least in in our world of environmetrics – there's a lot of standards already in place and it sounds like some other repositories already have some of those.

TOPS Moderator:

Do we have folks from other data repositories that would like to jump in?

Speaker 13:

All of our data is registered to what is called the Planetary Data System for information model. This allows us to derive **common metadata formatting standards** for more than 70 different missions and 700 different types of instrument systems that have been flown in the solar system. And it enables efficient search and recovery and usage of data. Especially to prepare for machine learning-type data and ready to use scenarios – we're in the middle of porting all of our data holdings to planetary data system for this information model if you will, came up over the last 10 years and has now been widely recognized across numerous space agencies that serve planetary data and it's the standard by which all of our data and many other different international institutions standardized and serve their data products.

Speaker 2:

A little bit on the comments made by [Speaker 7] and the contributions of my colleagues who are managing repositories – I think from the side of the faculty, one of the struggles, or the challenges that we face is — is the creation and the maintenance of the data. When we create data, it's associated with the particular project and a particular enterprise. And that's the star. We can follow certain principles to release it. But then the next step is how can we maintain it? I listened to few comments from my colleagues that they welcome the data and they incorporated following...principles etcetera. But at some point, one of the constraints that we face is to learn how can we do this? And to see if this effort requires us to continue updating the database. Or do we just deliver these and that's done deal right – that we finished this contribution and that's it. I think that connection, that training in the **whole pipeline** from the generation of the data, all the way to the creation is tremendously important to understand and to define or to identify what would be the key connections between repositories and those that are generating the data.

TOPS moderator:

I think that's a great point.

Speaker 14:

I've just been putting a few points in the chat – just to point out things that are said – there in the lessons that might be useful to note there. I think the things to stress here is that – and please, understand TOPS is not the first organization to think about this – there's an enormous amount of other work that's out there, and you shouldn't feel like you're trying to create stuff, or do things from scratch.

Reach out to your local research community. Reach out to your local library, the data managers and so on. All those folks are there to help you with respect to thinking about topics such as metadata and so on. You, as a researcher should not be – we're talking about researchers here who are on this call – don't feel like you have to figure out what FAIR means for your data. There are people out there who can help you. And there's also loads of resources that are out there that you can take and these things that we're trying to catalog in this particular session of resources. But again to stress – you're not on your own here and there are loads of organizations that are providing materials that can help you out.

TOPS Moderator:

Thank you for that [Speaker 14].

Speaker 14:

Thanks [Speaker] for that point on FORTT. My apologies for not mentioning that one – those things that are there—

TOPS Moderator:

I will say one thing that we're doing around our curriculum is – and the goal is not to reinvent the wheel. We realize that there's been folks who've been doing this work for decades and bringing in open science subject matter experts (SMEs) who have been contributing to the space and leveraging the work that they've been doing.

The open competitive paid opportunities because we realized that the stuff that's needed to teach open science is out there. I mean, we really want to lean in and ensure that folks have the infrastructure to be successful in this. And so, I really appreciate your thoughts. Our breakout room will be closing in two minutes and I hate when I get immediately thrown out the breakout room. So, I want to hold space for folks. Is there anything else that folks want to discuss around? How we're talking about open data? Has anyone had an experience where they would like to ensure that we include in our open data modules as we work with the subject matter experts?

Speaker 6:

I would like to share my experience. But a quick thank you. I'm new to open science and I'm coming from a completely different industry, which is banking, and I did some mechatronics course through Amazon and I've been reading some chemistry books and Earth science books. I used to publish some articles on social media regarding banking and financial technology and from there I gained some experience in publishing and in writing articles. And then for the past few years I've been watching and reading the social media of NASA and researching some topics and getting some subjects on Google and I got some –

TOPS Moderator:

Oh no, it looks like we're being moved back.

###

END OF TRANSCRIPT

BEGINNING OF CHAT TEXT

1:52 PM [Speaker 14]

In one of the lessons, we discuss who you can reach out to. This includes your own research community, your local library or data services, open science related communities such as Reproducibility. Don't feel that you are on your own!

1:54 PM

+100 to [Speaker14]

1:54 PM

+1 to what [Speaker14] just said. Here is a resource that might be helpful in devising training: <https://forrt.org/syllabus/>

1:55 PM

Will the lessons be continuously updated and refined in the future? e.g., to account for feedback

1:57 PM

Importance of metadata in aiding discovery

END OF CHAT TEXT

JAMBOARD NOTES (Slide #3)

1. What is important to cover in this lesson?
 - Consistency in data dictionaries
 - No training in data management at the grad or even postdoc level!
 - I don't think we can point to a universal data format. OTOH what we have done is a) recommend that researchers make use of Open formats (i.e. non-proprietary formats that are available) and b) use sources such as FAIRsharing.org which catalogues the formats out there.
 - NMDC - National Microbiome Data Collaborative is one example of a community effort to improve microbiome data <https://microbiomedata.org/>

- Here is a resource that might be helpful in devising training:
<https://forrt.org/syllabus/>
2. Any proposed changes to the structure?
 - Will the lessons be continuously updated and refined in the future? E.g., to account for feedback?
 3. What practical or hands-on experience should a beginner gain from this module?
 - Data management skills – maybe how to write data management plan
 - Importance of metadata in aiding discovery
 4. What is important to the topic, but not critical for a beginner to learn?
 - In one of the lessons, we discuss who you can reach out to. This includes your own research community, your local library or data services, open science related communities such as reproducibility. Don't feel that you are on your own!

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NASA TOPS Moderator: Steve Crawford

BEGINNING OF TRANSCRIPT

TOPS Moderator:

Alright. Well, thanks everyone for joining. I'm Steve Crawford. I am the Science Data Officer in the Open-Source Science Initiative (OSSI) here at NASA headquarters. Thanks for your interest in joining the software section.

And I'll just post this here again [the link to the Jamboard]. The proposed module structure, which is an introduction to open software using open software, making open software and sharing open software. And the questions that we'd like to ask you and hear some of your feedback on are: [Reading from the Jamboard] what is important to cover in the in these lessons? What is important to the topic but not critical for a beginner to learn? What practical or hands-on experience should a beginner gain from the module and any proposed changes to the structure?

And so please feel free to come off mute and I'm going to bring up the Jamboard here. Right now, there is a small number of us. So, let's just jump right in. And it would be great to hear what some of your thoughts are.

Speaker 1:

I'm not too familiar with contributing to open software. I'm curious as to what the aim is here? Like how much of an introduction do we want to go over?

TOPS Moderator:

And I think that is part of the conversation that we want to have is, what is an important topic to cover in this introduction? For someone who hasn't – maybe you're a good case example here – in terms of what would you like to know? As an introduction that would help you either feel more comfortable contributing to open-source software or will be useful for doing your research?

Speaker 1:

Okay, I put the little sticky note up there [on the Jamboard]. Yeah, talking about licensing...I think that's a huge can of worms, especially at NASA, we're pretty restricted to – I think it's like two types of licensing that we can do — but I think that's a pretty obscure [thing] for most beginners, but also something that could be important to discuss.

TOPS Moderator:

That's a great topic to cover as it is an important one. One which can be quite new to people who aren't familiar to it. I'll repost the link to the Jamboard. Does anyone else want to come off mute and share their thoughts?

Speaker 2:

Thanks, [TOPS Moderator], for putting this all together. First of all, I think it's really an awesome kind of forum for people to share ideas and everything. I think it's really effective for the community. I guess I will add a sticky note [on the Jamboard] just to get it on paper, but one thing that I think is really important is going to be **security practices** and as a beginner – it might be a little overwhelming for folks, but there are definitely **best practices** that can keep people's information safe, especially in an open-source kind of format.

Things like **storing credentials in your code**? Something like that. Something that's so simple – that might not come to people outside of the field. So really **software development practices** in the context of security will be pretty important.

TOPS Moderator:

That's a great point. I know I've made that mistake before. I think everyone's done it at least once. And it's definitely a good thing to make people aware about.

Speaker 3:

I want to add something on the security topic. There is an enterprise from UC Berkeley and it's for open-source projects or for individual researchers who are trying to do this. That topic can be daunting and overwhelming and it requires fairly specialized domain knowledge that is often separate from the person's scientific domain. And so that's an area where a program like TOPS (Transform to Open Science) could have a huge benefit and you don't need a lot of this, but you need some of it in the right time. For example, having a team that is sponsored by NASA, that could parachute in and do effectively a little bit of an audit and consulting of best practices for a small project to get going in the right direction and harmonizing how that's done in Jupyter. At this point we're large enough that we actually have the security team and we've had people mostly from DOE (Department of Energy) who have effectively volunteered because they use Jupyter and DOE.

For our [software] deployments – they've volunteered to formally lead a structured security team and they do it and it's fabulous, but that's not very viable for smaller, individual projects. And so, if TOPS or the NASA team had a small team of specialists who could do this audit, give some tips and have a summary of "these are the best practices and in an easy to find location", I bet for the majority of projects that would be sufficient and it could have a big impact. [Would also help with] making that practice harmonized across projects, which is

a big benefit. One of the problems with security is what I would call “unnecessary variability” in things that are different for no good reason other than accidental variability and **harmonizing** that makes it much easier to audit and to know that things are being done right. So just an idea for the rest of the TOPS team.

TOPS Moderator:

Yeah, thanks for that comment. I think that's a great thought. Looks like we have a few more people joining.

Now I'll add the Jamboard link. Feel free to come off mute if you want. What we're basically looking at is adding ideas of either: [Reading from the Jamboard] What is important to cover in this lesson? Or what is an important topic but not critical for a beginner to learn? I think those are the two that have generated a number of ideas so far. Maybe we'll save that for the last 10 minutes. The practical or hands-on experiences people should gain and generating ideas around that. But feel free to either add a note to the Jamboard or come off mute and share your thoughts. We are recording a transcription of [this discussion] and that way we can make sure we capture everyone's comments.

Speaker 3:

I'll add a second topic to expand on which I'm still working on – the science software — software and I'm going to interpret that the way I'm thinking. It may not have been the original intent, but I teach software engineering for a science course...Even though the domain specific work is put in...[TOPS Core Team Member] has been a guest lecture on earth science. But the big debate, and I think the struggle that I've seen in my students but have also seen it in in professional scientists, is that balance between **am I doing the right thing in terms of open science and reproducibility with my code, versus where do I turn into a software engineer?** And that's not my job, right.

And I think understanding and helping people understand that it's a spectrum. It's not a binary, right? It's not a “yes”. You [do not] have to flip into a software engineering role and then all of a sudden have this very high burden to meet in terms of infrastructure and so on and so forth. But rather, that it's a spectrum and it's okay if you put some code on GitHub where you explicitly say “this is not necessarily a fully tested reusable community tool that I commit to maintaining for the next 20 years of my life.” These are the supporting scripts and notebooks that I've made and maybe here's a small tool for this particular paper. It's documented to the best of my ability, but I need to move on. **That's already an advance in terms of making software part of science.** It will help someone else pick that up, right? It will help other researchers build upon it. Maybe somebody else gets an idea from that and then builds an actual reusable tool later on, but that doesn't necessarily have to be always the case.

And it's legitimate to say “the scripts that accompany this paper were only written for this particular data set. And I have no intention in turning this into a long-term

project.” You can still do certain things in terms of how you share them, **how do you document them?** You should still license it clearly so people know under what conditions to use it, but that burden can be met with minimal effort without necessarily becoming a software engineer. And I think clarifying where in that spectrum people can live, and how they can move back and forth along that spectrum in different projects or points in their career is really important because otherwise I see that it feels like, “Oh my God, I can't do all of this. This is too much. That's not my job.”

TOPS Moderator:

That's a great point.

Speaker 4:

The NASA Open-source software policies report from the National Academies has precisely that discussion, by the way.

Speaker 3:

Thanks, [Speaker 4].

TOPS Moderator:

I know I reference that report all the time.

Speaker 3:

That's a fantastic resource.

TOPS Moderator:

It's a great resource. And here's the link to the Jamboard, for those who've been joining – feel free to add your thoughts to there or come off mute and share your thoughts.

I know we've gotten some of the important lessons to cover and some of the critical topics. Are there some things – like some hands-on experiences or examples that you've completed or experienced?

Speaker 2:

I guess as a note, [TOPS Moderator], I'll just say this kind of more in an abstract manner. One thing that I would really like to take away from – if this is in the context of a training module – [would be to] really get a good survey of what is available to me as an astronomer or as an enthusiast or whatever my level might be. But really to understand what's out there and maybe not necessarily how to use all of it. I don't plan on learning Force Photometry, in a couple hours.

The training module – but really understanding like I mentioned – understanding what software is there and its applicability to the use cases I'm looking for.

TOPS Moderator:

And would aspects of “here are the next steps” be helpful?

Speaker 2:

Right, right. Absolutely. And maybe even some use cases, some explicitly stated use cases for some of this open software being developed.

TOPS Moderator:

Another question we can ask is: what are the biggest challenges that you're currently facing? Where TOPS or this curriculum could help support you? What are the areas, especially around software that you're most worried about? And feel free to say anything right now.

Maybe another way to say is — when you were starting out, what were the obstacles, especially related to software that you found difficult to overcome?

Speaker 1:

I mean one bottleneck – I guess you can call it that – I've seen with a lot of scientists going through open-source software is the **adaptation for an open-source process**. It hasn't gone through any adaptation to science specifically like the existing process is meant for very much like what we have up on the board is tech software rather than science software. And so, there's a lot of requirements that scientists have to meet that don't necessarily apply to their development because it's not expected to be structured the same way as tech software is – at least within NASA.

Speaker 5:

Hi (Name) here. I'm a programmer, so I guess let me just [share] one thing I've observed; I'll have code that I am maintaining with a proper GitHub repository and somebody will take a segment of it and repurpose it. And maybe update or fix it for their particular use case. I've noticed that occasionally, the person who's adapting the code for another use case, isn't quite familiar with how to use GitHub or not quite comfortable with it. We've ran into situations where we'll be able to say, “oh, we have this new data set that was based on code that we adapted”, and then locating that adapted code becomes difficult. So basically, **we go from a version-controlled system to spinoffs that are not version controlled and take on a life of their own**.

So, if there could be training to get people comfortable with – okay, if I need to make changes to this code that is version controlled, how do I do that in a way that doesn't spin off into this non-version controlled version?

TOPS Moderator:

I'm going to add that to the practical experience of interacting with projects on GitHub [on the Jamboard]. I think that's a great point. Other thoughts? Anyone else?

Speaker 5:

Sorry, a second thought popped up. Including the description of the kind of environment setup that's required to run the software. Because I've run into situations where the code is there, but an explanation of the dependencies or the required versions is lacking.

So, I think that's a good practice to get into people's mind is not only should you be keeping track of your software, but **keeping track of the context and dependencies** that make the software work in a reproducible way.

TOPS Moderator:

I think that could go under several different areas here [on the Jamboard]. Added it to here [the Jamboard], but I think that's a good point as well.

We have a small group here, so we can also open this up. I'm not sure if we are going to get pulled back [into the main room] or not. I think maybe in in the last five minutes.

But are there other concerns or other areas that you're thinking about or things that you'd like to see come out of this? This is a chance — obviously you can provide feedback on our GitHub or by emailing us or other additional ways. But this is also our opportunity for us to engage with your thoughts.

Speaker 4:

I think one issue that's important to cover in regards to licenses is the hurdles that are associated with **copyleft licenses**. Many times, people think that a copyleft license is beneficial because they have this kind of aspiration for continued open source of whatever derivative works may appear, but they don't realize that this post imposes a lot of restrictions on people. So there's a misconception regarding the difference between copyleft and permissive licenses. That is very important for research purposes, I think.

TOPS Moderator:

I think that's definitely a good point. I know that's also conversations that I've experienced in the past.

Speaker 3:

I want to second how important that is. I think many people coming from an academic mindset think “oh, it's only an issue for commercial projects”, but that's not the case, right? Jupyter and [others], the vast majority of the scientific Python ecosystem. We made a very deliberate and concerted choice to harmonize around **BSD** (Berkeley Software Distribution license) and BSD type licenses a long time ago. I'll post a link to the public rationale for that, which is something that John Hunter wrote in 2004 and one of the reasons was precisely so that code could flow between projects unimpeded and whenever there's a single **GPL** (GNU general public license) project in that ecosystem, it's a one-way valve,

right? Code can flow from the rest of the ecosystem into the GPL project, but it can't come back out, but we occasionally encounter projects where somebody develops a Jupyter tool based on all of the Jupyter machine, right? But that specific tool is GPL automatically, we can't use it right? Even Jupyter itself is not allowed to use that new tool which is built on Jupyter.

I can't incorporate them back, we couldn't say, "oh, we went back to becoming an official tool because the GPL is a one-way valve". So, the point that [Speaker 4] is making is a point that has a big impact, even for the open-source community and the program like NASA – I think interoperability can help folks understand [the ecosystem] better.

TOPS Moderator:

[Speaker 6], did you have something to add? I see you came on video.

Speaker 6:

I put my video on to nod strongly in agreement with [Speaker 3].

TOPS Moderator:

I know you've come in a little bit later. Don't know if there's any of these topics of what is important to cover or any proposed changes or any practical hands-on experience or aspects of important topics, but things for more advanced than beginner that if you'd like to contribute your thoughts. Or if anybody else has popped up with any additional thoughts.

Speaker 6:

Sorry it took me a while to get to this session because I kept getting put in the wrong one, but I'm particularly interested in this **reproducible environment** session or question because it's an area that, at least in my domain astrophysics, is a big problem. It's not actually a big problem – it's not a technical problem – it's a sociological problem, right? It's that most scientists don't know or can't be bothered, depending on your perspective and understanding, how to build a reproducible environment, even though the tool exists. Five or ten years ago now, the tools really did exist to do it, so I think there is a big opportunity to actually educate people on that because it's one of the areas where the tech has appeared recently to do it effectively. But the knowledge really doesn't exist in the science side of the story.

Speaker 5:

Yeah, I just totally agree.

One thing I would note – you're making me think of some of these tools for things like containers and continuous integration. And I think one thing that may be emphasized is there's this idea that there is an overhead that comes with maintaining good open-source practices. But there also has been a big growth in automating a lot of that overhead. So, I feel like that could be something to think

about introducing as a way of maintaining things in a reproducible open-source way. It can have a cost over time if you do it manually or if you automate it right. It can have a larger upfront cost, but then you kind of get those benefits without having to spend a bunch of extra man hours.

I've been learning this a lot recently and I don't know if it's something that folks are necessarily aware of. They're just maybe thinking "oh, man, this is going to add four extra hours a week just to make sure that everything is documented and maintained". But it doesn't have to be that way.

Speaker 6:

Totally. I do a lot of workshops with members of my science community. And I always lead off with the question "why should you care about this"? It's not because "you're a good member of the community". It's entirely for the future, your future. You will benefit from this more than you can possibly imagine.

TOPS Moderator:

I think the breakout [room] will be closing in about one minute, so does anyone have any final thoughts? I think [Speaker 6]'s final thought is a really good one for consideration. **How useful this can be to your future self**, is a great point.

And before we close or before the [breakout] room closes, I will thank everyone for your participation and also your knowledge. We are very interested in this topic and so this is why we're doing things like TOPS and to help support the community and help build on all the work everyone has done. And so, your feedback is incredibly helpful and appreciated.

And I think we'll probably start disappearing soon.

###

END OF TRANSCRIPT

BEGINNING OF CHAT TEXT

1:30 PM [TOPS Moderator]

https://jamboard.google.com/d/1cibN6Xf-ZEKmMFXVsLI9GlaHSdUNlo-22LExcid_3sU/viewer?f=3

1:33 PM

Licensing is a big issue for sure!

1:42 PM [Speaker 4]

<https://nap.nationalacademies.org/catalog/25217/open-source-software-policy-options-for-nasa-earth-and-space-sciences>

1:43 PM [Speaker 4]

[Speaker 3]: see Table 2.1

in <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/read/25217/chapter/4>

1:48 PM

True

1:48 PM [Speaker 2]

Have to sign off for another meeting, thanks for everything, enjoyed the conversation!

1:53 PM [Speaker 4]

Why we should be using BSD. John Hunter - 16 Dec 2004.

http://nipy.sourceforge.net/software/license/johns_bsd_pitch.html

1:53 PM [Speaker 3]

Thx [Speaker 4]!

1:57 PM [Speaker 3]

Thank you, and good luck with the rest of the amazing TOPS work!

END OF CHAT TEXT

JAMBOARD NOTES

1. What is important to cover in this lesson?
 - Types of licensing, or no licensing
 - Good/thorough documentation
 - Science SW (software) versus Tech SW (software)
 - Producing a reproducible environment
 - Security practices, “science wants to be free” actually its “steal this scientific SW (software)” – Abbie Hoffman
 - John Hunter – 16 Dec 2004. “Why we should be using BSD”. Link: http://nipy.sourceforge.net/software/license/johns_bsd_pitch.html
2. Any proposed changes to the structure?
 - Collaborative scientific functionality development versus abstract idea sharing
 - Guidance for civil servants who cannot sign most license agreements
 - Adaptation of software release procedure for science software specifically
3. What practical or hands-on experience should a beginner gain from this module?
 - Practicable experience of interacting with projects on GitHub

4. What is important to the topic, but not critical for a beginner to learn?
- Peer review process
 - Deployment (e.g. docker images, software channels)

Open Tools Breakout Session

August 11, 2022

TOPS Community Forum

Verbal Discussion and Chat Text

Anonymous Transcript

NASA TOPS Moderators: Isabella Martinez and Danielle Groenen

BEGINNING OF TRANSCRIPT

TOPS Moderator:

Thank you, Danielle, for starting the transcription.

So, we may have a couple more folks joining us in a minute. I know that not everybody was able to register ahead of time. But I think let's get started to make good use of this 30 minutes of time. So hopefully I am displaying a slide. Fantastic.

So, we are capturing today's discussion, rather than through a recording, through a transcription of the breakout room that will be anonymized as well as capturing what is written in the Jamboard. So, this is the open tools breakout room.

Okay, there might be some shuffling around of breakout rooms if you are in the wrong room. I think the person you need to message is (Name), but I'm not entirely sure how to do that.

Alright so, I'm going to begin by introducing a few of the open science module topics which our open science subject matter experts (SMEs) have been introducing, as they've been working on the open core content over the past few weeks.

[Reading Slide]

These multiple topics explain how open science tools encourage open science, using FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles. To identify open science communities and initiatives within and across disciplines, and to join the community of practice of interest to the learner. To provide examples of how open science is practiced in research teams. To identify types of open science tools along with their purpose. To match appropriate open science tools to specific objectives within the research workflow, and then to describe three to five open science tools and how to use them.

As I introduced earlier, this [slide] is the structure that we are trying to follow. Our goal is to introduce open science tools generally and then go into a couple of examples for open data, open software, open results and then talk about

community stories of using those tools. So, I've got a few questions on the left here to get the discussion started. By no means do we need to follow the questions or agenda that I've set out for today.

Because today is for us to hear from you.

I've been messaged by my colleagues that it is taking a little bit of time for people to join the breakout rooms in a couple of ways and a couple of places, so the group that's discussing this may be getting larger as we begin talking.

Alright, does anyone feel called to begin the discussion, perhaps by answering the question: what do you believe is important to cover in the open tools lesson? Feel free to unmute yourself or to post in the chat.

Speaker 1:

I think part of the mental indigestion that we're having is sort of what our target really is. This is so broad. I've been participating in open science for the last three or four years. I'm part of this **Pangeo** community that I know [name] was part of, and we've done a lot of things regarding tooling and mostly in **Python** to enable open science. But I don't know if that even belongs here. I don't know exactly. So, I bet a lot of other people who are on this call have some experience in the open science communities and they've poked at different parts of this ecosystem.

I think it would be good to do a survey of all the different kinds of organizations or groups that have actually had success in this arena before. One thing that worries me is this sort of feeling that we are starting from scratch, because I don't think we're starting from zero here in this community for sure.

TOPS Moderator:

Yeah, definitely the case. And we have quite an extensive list of curated tools. You mentioned the **Pangeo** community – **The Carpentries** is another good example. They have a very extensive list of tools as well as workshops that folks can join. But the reason that we wanted to have this as a topic during the Community Forum today was to specifically get the perspective of people who are NASA scientists. And what are the tools that you think are best suited for a beginner? Or someone who is doing work with NASA? The way that I got started with open science was 100% through open-source software and through **GitHub**, but that is not the only tool that's out there.

And so, we wanted to get all of your experience and perspectives of the tools that you mentioned and see where else they appear in these curated lists of tools anyone can use. Because tools are domain-specific sometimes and we won't know what you feel is the best tool for your domain unless people give us that information.

Speaker 1:

I mean, if you just want more experience...I'm trying to work with a NASA data set right now that's not available...it wasn't available on **object storage** somewhere, which would make it accessible to everyone in an efficient and open way.

And it wasn't quite clear how actually to proceed with that kind of a request, but that's not really a tooling thing. I hope we're moving more towards less of API (Application Programming Interface) and registration kind of stuff and more actual openness and access — fundamental access to the foundational data in a way that is out there and accessible to everyone without registration walls and service restrictions. I don't know how to capture that into some useful way for the purpose of this conversation now.

TOPS Moderator:

I would say that what you just said is incredibly useful and definitely being able to identify what we need tools for, I would say is probably the first step to choosing a tool.

[Chat 1] put something in the chat. [Reads aloud the text in the chat] My thought is a good start (for a total beginner) is what problem are we trying to solve with the tools? What steps to use the tools (what are the free resources to learn **Python**), how to use **Anaconda, Jupyter Labs** and then how to present the findings from a tool?

I think you bring up an interesting point that I would be interested in hearing other people's take on, which is similar to what [Speaker 1] was just saying about identifying the problem that you're trying to solve with the tool, is probably something that's worth going over in this module. And if anyone has any thoughts about how approaching a problem from an open mindset might be different from another mindset that is also an interesting question that's not necessarily on the slide that if anyone has thoughts on, we'd be happy to hear and capture.

Speaker 2:

My name's (Name). So, I just wondering – it occurred to me that one way to approach this might be to come up with a couple of use cases for different users, like say, a graduate student researcher, first exposed to NASA science, and what might be useful for them. Another use case could be a project scientist for a bigger NASA project. You know, for a broad swath of people. It might give them clues or insights into how they could approach what open tools might be useful for them and what approach that they could take. So, I'm familiar with this kind of use case scenario idea – I think people typically do it when they're developing software and trying to scope out what features should be in there as well. So, it might be a good way to scope out the curriculum in this case as well.

TOPS Moderator:

I know that there was discussion at one point in time, specifically about if you are using an API and doing open science.

Even if you're just getting started with open science, maybe particularly in that case, you're going to need different tools than if you're a graduate student on part of a larger team, and not necessarily in charge of the entire management. So, I like the idea of perhaps breaking it down that way. Thank you so much for sharing that perspective.

Speaker 3:

This is (Name). So, I just wanted to say I see that some of the biggest hurdles for usage of data – I was kind of torn on whether or not to go to data access or open tools here, but I think tools are kind of the key to addressing these issues of just being able to find the data sets that you need and to be able to access them. And so, I think tools play a key part for, especially for the new scientists or the grad students who know they need a certain type of data, they just don't know where to find it.

Yeah, you're talking about in the less open environment. Sometimes you get data from your colleagues and the people they know and by word of mouth. So, I think it's important in the open tools arena to make sure we have the ability to search and discover and then make it easy to access.

TOPS Moderator:

Do you feel that has a home here in the open tools module? Or do you think that that discussion is better suited for the open data module?

Speaker 3:

Well, to me the open tools module was more relevant to me as a data provider – being able to do the appropriate things to make your data available. So, I came here with that perspective.

You know you need to be able to discover and find data. And so, I think tools need to be accessible that are separable from the actual data providers and the open data policies. But just to have the tools that integrate with those policies, so the data providers are presumably using standard metadata schemas and that sort of thing. And so having tools that are interoperable with those standards to make it more usable.

TOPS Moderator:

That is an excellent perspective. Thank you so much for sharing. [Speaker 4] I'll get to you in a moment, but [Chat 2] put something in the chat. I just wanted to read it out. [Reads aloud from text in the chat] From an equity perspective, most users outside the US and in some communities don't have the computation or bandwidth to handle level one (Level 1) NASA satellite datasets. Having cloud computing resources available (**Jupyterhub** or a **Google Colab**-like resource)

available with common software packages, an Earthdata login with all NASA data available would seem a way to level the playing field. Costs and security would have to be managed.

Do you have anything to add to that? Thank you so much for sharing.

Speaker 5:

Yeah, I think that, resources like at our institution – we can have petabyte storage and cloud computation on site, but you want to expand access to community colleges or other institutions like URM (Under-Represented Minority) schools and even within the US. Let alone outside the US, I think the computation is one big hurdle. You have scientists who are capable of analyzing the data, but they just don't have the resources.

TOPS Moderator:

I think you're definitely right. There was definitely talk about how much should we talk about cloud computing, as part of the open core versus maybe being a more specific module, because I think we could probably do 5 full lessons just on cloud computing and computational resources, but pointing to a way that users can find those resources might be well suited to the Open Tools section.

Speaker 5:

Yeah, I'll just add that the **National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)** just opened up access for any university access within the US to their visualization computer.

TOPS Moderator:

Oh, that's fantastic. And [Speaker 4], thank you so much for patiently waiting.

Speaker 4:

No problem at all. So, if you're going to discuss open tools, how are you going to address closed tools, especially with researchers who have established workflows with things that don't quite fit in that model, cause I've seen that issue, right? People have ways of working — they want to do part of the old way, part of the new way. How do I use closed tools on an open platform or vice versa? Anyways, that's just a point to discuss because I see that as being a problem.

TOPS Moderator:

It needs to be addressed. Do you have any solutions?

Speaker 4:

Well, so my solution is to not do any purity tests on openness. So, with our organization – who actually does supply and manage **Jupyter hubs** to other organizations? I think one of our partners said, well, we want to use **MATLAB** in the cloud and we went well, that's fine. We can work with that. But as long as you provide the license, even though it's sitting on top of open tools, if that's what you

need – I know there's a lot of highly specialized engineering software out there which doesn't have an open equivalent.

You have to provide that so you meet people where they're at in terms of reducing their barriers to getting the science done. Definitely no purity tests on whether or not a software tool is open, whatever you want to define that as.

TOPS Moderator:

What you just brought up speaks a lot to me because when I moved from my undergraduate institution to my graduate institution, I actually lost my MATLAB license and did not get it back. I had to learn R, and essentially relearn everything that I had learned to do over four years of undergraduate in order to be able to finish my graduate studies.

Would anyone like to speak to that particular topic that [Speaker 4] just brought up – the idea of maybe incorporating or at least acknowledging the use of closed tools in some areas in this module?

Speaker 3:

For me, I see it's really about interfaces. If they are using layers of abstraction and being able to interface. So, if you have a **common access layer**. I deal with web services so if you have a standard web service for accessing data, these closed tools could also use those open interfaces. So, I think as long as the coupling isn't too tight, we can maintain interoperability between closed and open tools.

TOPS Moderator:

And apologies if I mispronounce your name, [Speaker 6], would you like to jump in?

Speaker 6:

This is (Name) here. Thank you. So, I particularly believe that early learning general programming languages would be crucial. So that when it comes to the tool, it becomes unmaterialistic and using any and every tool will be that easy – actually particular modularity will be one such key takeaway when it comes to open tools. Thank you.

TOPS Moderator:

Yeah, I think that's a very good point. We are likely going to point to code learning resources already created by our collaborators rather than having a module that is dedicated to learning how to code within the open core. And each module is only going to be about 2 hours long and it's a lot of information to cover, but I definitely think that that is a good point.

Let's move to [Speaker 7].

Speaker 7:

So, when you're asking about closed tools versus open tools in this module, are you talking about the course content you want to highlight specifically in this curriculum?

That's more of a question than a comment. Because if we are discussing the intersections between closed and open tools, I think it could be very useful to do some sort of cartography about what kind of things closed tools and open tools are currently capable of and what are potentially the differences in scale that you can get from a closed and open tool. Keeping in mind that both open tool sets and closed tool sets are going to keep expanding. But hopefully open tool sets can expand into some of the space that is currently cordoned off for closed tools.

TOPS Moderator:

I think that that is an excellent suggestion.

Speaker 7:

Thank you.

TOPS Moderator:

Because you wouldn't know what kind of tools you need, unless you have an understanding of what can only be accomplished using closed tools versus open tools.

Speaker 7:

And overall, I think that where we are right now, there's a big need for an understanding of what we actually have that is in fully open versus fully closed. So, understanding what the current accessible stack of tools is in all the different fields that open science is enabling or at least trying to enable. But I think that's a need that needs to be addressed – what is the open stack and whether it has gaps.

TOPS Moderator:

I feel like we could have an entire community forum session on just that topic and I might suggest doing that to the rest of the TOPS team.

Speaker 7:

Sounds great. Hope to be there.

TOPS Moderator:

Thank you. And thank you, [TOPS Moderator], for putting the question into the chat.

Does anyone have any other comments on closed versus open tools and how to describe them in this module? We are also able to go on to another topic if people are feeling called to discuss another topic.

Speaker 2:

Earlier, you mentioned [TOPS Moderator], that there's already kind of a list that the TOPS team have come up with for open tools. Is that on the GitHub?

TOPS Moderator:

Yes, let me show you. Open Tools on TOPS GitHub.

Speaker 2:

Because that might be able to compliment the discussion with the closed tools.

TOPS Moderator:

We are in the process of forming the list of tools, but the idea was to think of three to five tools that would be described in-depth and perhaps have some practical hands-on exercises with massive online courses (MOOCs) to use them.

And so, something that I'm interested in gathering from all of you today is: do you have an open tool that you like to use and that you use all the time? Feel free to put that in the chat or in the Jamboard. But also feel free to unmute yourself and share to see if we can get the discussion started.

Speaker 2:

Can I just ask one more thing? I guess at this level where we have a whole bunch of people from different backgrounds – should the focus be on tools for the widest range of use? So, are GitHub or Teams the kind of tools that you're thinking about?

TOPS Moderator:

Those are definitely good to know, but I'm actually interested in what are the domain specific tools that you are using? What are the ones that I probably haven't heard of? Because I only study in one field.

Speaker 1:

I put into the chat the tools that I use and a lot of the folks that I work with at USGS and in ASA and that the EPA are using – the reason we use that tool set is because it came from the community – we didn't build anything new really, I mean we just kept enhancing things and making everything work better.

You know, folks across all these different agencies working together on these things that are all common, it's like a **super flexible, scalable tool set** that can handle this – is what I tell the people about anything that's going to come down the road. And that's why we should be supporting this and using it. That doesn't mean we're there yet and it doesn't mean that probably 95% of the scientific community doesn't understand it. So that's why I'm excited about this project and projects like project **Pythia** to help try to get more traction within the open side, the research community, because only a few people know about these powerful

tools that exist right now, and so they don't know how to use them. And also, they don't know how to look for supporting them when they make their proposals or whatever kind of work they're doing.

Yes. So [Speaker 5] is on the same wavelength, right? The open source – the open Python stack.

TOPS Moderator 2:

Did we get to [Speaker 8's] question yet?

Speaker 8:

I don't think so. Because mine is more of a comment. That might be a resource for you guys. UNESCO...they're an organization with a call for open science or the recommendation for open science (**UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science**). They have a web tool which allows you to send them open resources. And that's been up for a couple of months. So maybe there's a way that you can get access to that data, since NASA and UNESCO – don't know how close they can work together, but they have been collecting the data specifically on compiling resources so that might be a helpful repository for you guys to try and access.

A question about the concept of tools. I'm mostly pre-research, but are we talking only about software tools? Because as a synthetic biologist my mind goes to things like **Free Genes** or the **Open Yeast** network or anything that's like – there's a lot of computational biology tools that are really specific, but there's also actual material transfer or physical tools that I feel like are necessary for doing open science.

TOPS Moderator:

I think that that is an excellent comment and I was actually about to say something about that because a lot of people are putting really great thoughts about tools in the chat. But yeah, I am not a biologist, so I wouldn't know about the open tools that are available for doing biology or chemistry. So, you mentioned a couple which I jotted down, but are there any others that you'd like to mention so we can capture it in the transcription?

Speaker 8:

Sure. So, **The Free Genes Project** is with Stanford, and then there's a bunch of other ones – **Open Bioeconomy Lab** is a big one. If you're looking for open science hardware. Specifically, I would go to the **GOSH** (Gathering for Open Science Hardware) Community Forum, which is global open science hardware community. That's a very active open science hardware community, touching on things other than biology. But they do a lot of work with biology and automating biology.

In terms of other synthetic biology related tools, let me see...I know that one of

our open science SMEs (Subject Matter Experts) mentioned about, I guess I don't know what to call this – like a loan program for lab mice and lab rats, which I had never heard before. I found it fascinating. So definitely stuff like that, which is domain specific – is also important for us to connect with even if it's not necessarily expanded upon in this in these particular modules.

I think that biology – I'm not sure about chemistry – but biology and synthetic biology specifically, requires some documentation because by the nature of the biological material transfer – it is expensive and they tend to not last for as long as an open tool which you can just post and it will stay up there forever. Somebody's job is to ship you freeze dried yeast or genes on a micro-like filter. That's why I think Stanford **Free Genes** is so impressive. Or also the **BioBricks Foundation** out of MIT and **iGEM** (International Genetically Engineered Machine). But they're really impressive because they've been sending out actual physical, biological materials for a long time now.

TOPS Moderator:

Does anybody else – we have two minutes left – have any domain-specific open science tools or communities that they want to put in the chat or say out loud so that we can capture it today? You'll also have access to the Jamboard afterwards.

So, I asked that question at the beginning, when we first joined the breakout session, about focusing on NASA data – those scientists from all over the States, from all different domains, and all across the world on collaborative interdisciplinary teams, use NASA funding to do their research. Yes, we are focusing on NASA scientists, but that definition means a very broad group of people. So hopefully that is a useful answer to your question. I have a couple other comments here.

[After reading the chat] Thank you, [Chat 3], for mentioning Raspberry pies.

Speaker 8:

There's **JOGL** (Just One Giant Lab) which is based in Paris, France. But it's a global open science community. **GOSH**, as I mentioned, is a subset of JOGL. **Friendzymes** is another synthetic biology community. In terms of tools, that's all I have that's super specific. I probably could find more, but those are the broad strokes.

TOPS Moderator:

Thank you so much for sharing that. Thank you so much for everyone who posted tools in the chat as well. [TOPS Moderator] and I have been capturing it all in the transcription.

###

END OF TRANSCRIPT

BEGINNING OF CHAT TEXT

1:27 PM

People can post virtual post-it notes in the Jamboard: https://jamboard.google.com/d/1cibN6Xf-ZEKmMFXVsLI9GlaHSdUNlo-22LExcjd_3sU/edit?usp=sharing

1:28 PM

I am proud to participate in this non-technical aspect of Open Science - Ethos.

1:31 PM [Chat 1]

My thought is a good start (for the total beginner) is what problem we are trying to solve with the tools, what steps to use the tools (what are the free resources to learn Python), how to use Anaconda/jupyter labs, and how to present the findings from a tool.

1:34 PM [Chat 2]

From an equity perspective, most users outside the US and in some communities don't have the computation or bandwidth to handle level 1 NASA satellite datasets. Having cloud computing resources available (jupyterhub or a Google Colab-like resource) available with common software packages, an earthdata login/ with all NASA data available would seem a way to level the playing field. Costs and security would have to be managed.

1:36 PM

+1 [Chat 2] this is mostly overlooked!

1:37 PM

Agree 100%

1:39 PM

Tools help produce data, which can be specific and unique depending on the user's usage to such tool(s)

1:39 PM

Also, the colab/jupyterhub approach fosters sharing/leveraging complicated software environments, which lowers the barrier to entry

1:40 PM

So, no tough love [Speaker]?

1:41 PM

I'll plead the 5th as an OSS evangelist

1:42 PM

But the workflows created with closed tools are not open

1:44 PM

If you have any particular code-learning resources to share please put in the chat!

1:45 PM

One other example in addition to MATLAB would be ArcGIS

1:45 PM

Programming language as a general course. I do believe this should be course in OCW. Cheers

1:45 PM

Ooh, and don't forget about IDL! 😊

1:46 PM

For me the open stack is python-based: fsspec, dask, xarray, holoviz, STAC

1:48 PM

Forgot geopandas. 😊

1:48 PM

Open tools that are freely accessible (open-source software) to more people would open up the opportunities for open science.

1:49 PM

Qt framework (there is a free for non-commercial use version)

1:49 PM

python, numpy, pandas, jupyter labs, github

1:50 PM

xarray, scikit-learn, scikit-image, scipy-stats, pandas, dask, matplotlib, github, hdf5, netcdf4, zarr, bokeh, tensorflow, jupyter lab

1:51 PM

pytorch! 😊

1:52 PM

Tools with good documentation are better appreciated. #Peace

1:52 PM

We need tools that work effectively with data on the cloud

1:53 PM

<https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>

1:53 PM

NASA Airborne Sciences have some specific data formats that require some rather boutique open-source tools

1:53 PM

Also, there is a lack of open advanced tools in the area of EDA for hardware design such as high-speed PCB design and advanced circuits simulators

1:53 PM

<https://forum.openhardware.science/>

1:54 PM

3D printer, for additive printing has been in the community for long time. :)

1:55 PM [Chat 3]

Uses of cheap and low-cost computing hardware, such as Raspberry Pi with data specific sensors

1:56 PM

Open data access APIs like OPeNDAP and HAPI.

1:57 PM

<https://jogl.io/>

END OF CHAT TEXT

FROM ATTENDEE:

I named a bunch of Open Science Communities and Tools, especially related to my field of Synthetic Biology, with the Open Tools Breakout Group for the transcription. If those didn't make it into the transcription I believe that this list includes the main tools/communities I mentioned.

Stanford Free Genes, The BioBrick Foundation with iGEM, GOSH, JOGL, Open BioEconomy Lab. Open Yeast Collection, Friendzymes

In addition to that I mentioned that UNESCO has an Open Science Mapping Database that they are also working on at: <https://en.unesco.org/feedback/mapping-open-and-internationally-relevant-open-science-capacity-building-and-training>

Open Results Breakout Session

August 11, 2022

TOPS Community Forum

Verbal Discussion and Chat Text

Anonymous Transcript

NASA TOPS Moderator: Yaitza Luna-Cruz

BEGINNING OF TRANSCRIPT

TOPS Moderator:

As Isabella mentioned before [in the general session], we are going to have this transcript made, but no recording will take place in this session to promote freedom of expression because we really want to hear from you.

And also, the transcript will be anonymized before it is shared with the community and all the comments that you make today are going to be used to further refine the open core curriculum. So, what is the main objective of this discussion? We would love to have your feedback about the balance of learning what is open results and the tools to do it. What are you expecting to learn with this curriculum – with this particular session – what will help you to move in the direction for open results?

I'm going to take a minute to read these suggested topics aloud and during this time, if you haven't already, make some notes and gather your thoughts and then after this brief overview about the open results module, I will proceed to an open discussion.

OK, the open results module could also be named Open Access, but the current objective seeks to go beyond simple publication of results, but also the importance of transparency, replicability, and reproducibility of those results. By the end of this module, learners will have an in-depth understanding of how open science principles help with increasing the reproducibility and replicability of research as well as guidelines by which to choose the best location to publish their research. Learners will have hands-on experience with creating a replicable open science workflow using a virtual research environment and practice with tools that make such a workflow possible.

And more of a higher [level?] discussion than some of the previous discussion topics is recommended for this model, mainly to allow the participants to share with one another the Open Access journals that they like to use, as well as allow them time to reflect on the pros and cons of the platform.

This is the final module of the open core. The activity is meant to be a final

project and it will ask for the creation of a full research [project? Experiment?] that incorporates multiple principles of open science. Key terms we envision for this module are here on the screen [displays the slide deck], so I'm going to pause here and just allow everyone to read the proposed topics for the module. And then we're going to have a discussion.

As mentioned before, here [indicating the slide deck] we have the proposed structure for the open results module and I invite you to share with us what you think. You can raise your hand. You can write in the chat and you can also use the Jamboard link that I put in the chat.

Let's start with the first question. When you see this objective and when you read through all the topics, what do you think is most important to cover in the open results module? As I mentioned, feel free to use the chat, use the Jamboard or just raise your hand. For the Jamboard, I need to highlight that we are in slide #5.

I'm just receiving communication that we are having issues with getting people in the room. They are trying to get more people in the rooms.

But meanwhile, if you have any comments, we are on the first question. What do you think is important to cover in the open results module? I see we have more people joining. Welcome, welcome.

We are hoping to have a conversation about the open results module. I will share – since we have more people – I'm going to go back in the presentation and show you a brief overview of the proposed module topics that we are incorporating in open results. I'm going to give you time to just go over this list of topics.

[Speaker 2] thank you for posting the GitHub link for this module as a reference. You can access that over there and there's an overview of the module in the GitHub page.

And the intention here is we really want to listen to the Community about if we are [heading] in the right direction – what do you think is important to cover in this lesson? You can put it in the chat. You can use the Jamboard link that is in the chat as well or you can raise your hand and we will have a conversation. Would anyone like to share? What do you think about the objectives of this open results module?

Speaker 1:

I have a question.

TOPS Moderator:

Yeah, sure, [Speaker 1].

Speaker 1:

How are you defining results as opposed to data or the conclusions written in a paper? What is your definition of results?

TOPS Moderator:

I think we are defining results as the overall – when you're doing research from start to finish – it's the overall workflow that results. How do you like to share those results? How do you get credit? Or how do you credit the people that contributed? If you see the topics [indicating slide deck] – that's how we are defining results and I mentioned before, that is not only simply publication of the final results of the research, but also the importance of transparency, replicability and reproducibility of those results.

The lesson is built in a way that the learners will have a deep understanding how open science principles help with increasing their reproducibility and replicability of research.

Speaker 1:

Still not sure how that differs from openly publishing my data or openly publishing the software tool stack, or the algorithm I used, or the lab tools used.

TOPS Moderator:

It is both. It's the “what are open results?” part is going to be covered in this lesson. But also, the tools that you need or could use to publish the results. I think it's going to cover both parts and one of the things that we are asking the community is what do you think about that balance? That balance for the community. If you think about someone that is taking this module for the first time, what is more important for this open core – is it the definition of the open results or is it the tools to get open results?

Speaker 1:

Sure. But the other rooms — there's a room discussing publishing open data, and there's a room discussing publishing open software. So, what is different about what this room is discussing? Or are we just discussing openly publishing papers?

TOPS Moderator:

This is the whole workflow. So open results are more about the open science workflow.

Speaker 2:

Hey, this is (Name). I'm one of the people that worked with the lead [Speaker 4] and with all of our subject matter experts to develop this lesson. I've shared the overview which I think may be helpful for responding to your question [Speaker 1]. I shared it in the chat if you want to read through that.

Speaker 1:

Sure. Thanks.

TOPS Moderator:

Thank you so much.

Speaker 1:

It's from your overview [Speaker 2] – this sounds like it would be a module that you would take before basically – as an intro – before you knew anything really about proficiency. Otherwise, it would quickly devolve into specifically, where do I publish my data? What metadata [do] I need to attach to it? How do I publish my software? It's going to devolve into specifics very quickly. Is this intended as an introductory module? What is open science, basically?

Speaker 2:

I should share with you the additional part which is above this – it says “in this lesson we covered this” and “in this lesson...” – what you're saying [about] the open data open software [modules] is all setting this up.

That's why I didn't include that. But like what you're saying, those are things covered in other modules, right? Definitely. And yes, this is for the beginner level, this is an audience definitely more towards that beginner level of “you're starting out in open science”.

TOPS Moderator:

Yeah, open core is the beginning of this curriculum that we are developing. And then when we have – we announced today that we're going to have other solicitations and other openings because we are trying to expand this curriculum in the future for more advanced users. But this one is just for starting with the level of someone that is never used open science before. And this is the 5th module, which is the final module of all open core.

Speaker 1:

That's interesting. So, this [module] comes at the end.

TOPS Moderator:

Yes.

Speaker 1:

That's not where would I would have imagined it based on the topics that you are proposing, but OK.

Speaker 3:

Hi.

TOPS Moderator:

And this is exactly what we are here for. Maybe you can make a note and recommend that this should be in a different order.

Speaker 3:

I'm in the same boat as [Speaker 1] on this one and this seems a little bit like a catch-all in the sense of the module has some pretty concrete things to say about data, software and tools.

There is nothing specific about publications which [Speaker 1] mentioned – This is obviously an important result, but I feel like maybe this section is kind of a catch all for the additional things that are not data or tools or software or publications in a peer reviewed journal. I feel like maybe we could be thinking about what sort of other results are part of the scientific process – maybe results are inclusive of things like presentations at a poster session, maybe even results are some sort of knowledge graph that you've produced in a paper that has some sort of machine-readable interpretation, and maybe that's data or not. So, I don't know. Maybe we can think about some other things and maybe having a few other things would help us identify what makes this a cohesive module.

Speaker 2:

By the way, I would also add, [Speaker 3]. Let's just say the data and software [modules are] covering those kinds of things. This module is an opportunity to talk about these other sorts of aspects of sharing your research and exactly what you said — presentations or papers are some of the things that this module can look into as well. So, you were on the right path though, and [Speaker 4] has joined us.

Speaker 4:

Hi everyone.

TOPS Moderator:

Hello. And also, I want to highlight the proposed module structure [shows slide deck]. It will start with an introduction of open results, using open results, making open results, and sharing open results. So, in that introduction to the open results, we can add different topics and how we are defining results. If you have any recommendation or any suggestions, we encourage you to put it in the Jamboard. Speak through that or use the chat.

Speaker 5:

I have a thought or comment on this. I understand the directionality of this particular module. I guess one thing that I see a lot that would be interesting in this is: How are you either **educating early career scientists or providing tools for them to understand or plan their impact?** So, planning impact comes before results. How do you road map your outputs and then determine what those outputs are – “UN” results – advance the field or advance science or

advance your own work. So really assessing impact before binning these results and I think that would be a really interesting approach because that's something I constantly ask scientists — what part of what you're doing would be the best to...the community and then going from there, I don't know if that fits in this or not.

TOPS Moderator:

Well, that's what we are exploring. We are exploring ideas of how to do this better. Thank you so much for that suggestion because I think that could be incorporated in this as an introduction before talking about results – what is the impact of the results? Thank you so much. If you have the chance to put it in the chat or in the Jamboard, we really appreciate it.

Thank you, [Speaker 5].

OK, so we are discussing what is important to cover in this lesson – in the open results module we have an introduction to open results, using open results, making open results, and sharing open results. But what do you think needs to be covered in this session? Are we missing something?

Speaker 1:

Where in the rest of the curriculum – because I don't see it headlined anywhere – is Open Access journals?

TOPS Moderator:

Open Access. Yeah, I talked about that part at the beginning – and correct me if I'm wrong – but part of this module includes the different tools to publish?

Speaker 1:

OK. But I don't see – in at least looking at the GitHub at the moment – there's nothing about formal publication. And that's probably the easiest hook in with somebody who's new to the whole concept of open science is to just point them at Open Access journals.

Speaker 4:

Can I hop in real quick?

TOPS Moderator:

Sure.

Speaker 4:

I'm the module lead for open results and we do have **Open Access** – so we go through all of the different types of Open Access journals within one of our lessons. It might not be reflected on the GitHub yet because there was some confusion over whether that belonged in the ethos or open results [modules]. But

we are covering it. And also, resources...so waiver programs and things like that – we also have that in there.

Speaker 1:

Cool. That makes sense. If this is a catchall, as somebody said earlier, then something I've struggled with is **introducing students and interns to the concept of open science**. [It] doesn't get taught anywhere formally, not to undergrads. Or maybe there could be a module in here or a topic on how to get students sped up rapidly.

TOPS Moderator:

I think that's part of the first module, which is “ethos of open science” – a general introduction of what is open science? So that's the first lesson.

Speaker 1:

Sure. But I would love to have tools that help me get my students up to speed.

TOPS Moderator:

OK. That's good. We need more tools for introducing open science to an early [audience for] engagement?

[Speaker 1 nods in agreement]

Thank you.

OK, sorry if I'm pronouncing your name wrong. But you can go ahead [Speaker 6].

Speaker 6:

Sorry, I thought you asked me a question. I put a comment in the chat, but that's a self-describing comment. Oh, my was my hand up. It's not supposed to be.

TOPS Moderator:

Don't worry. I have another hand raised. Go ahead [Speaker 7].

Speaker 7:

I was just wondering – maybe somewhat similar to [Speaker 1]'s comments. I wish in terms of the publishing Open Access journals, that's great to hear that, that will be covered. I was wondering if you all have thought about other ways of making the publications of the manuscript after it's been peer reviewed, openly available and some of the tools or resources that researchers might have to make their results in the article openly available – like authors rights kind of addendum set, giving them the information they need to empower them to be able to negotiate when they are trained to publish, to make the results more open. I would be interested to know if you all have thought of that, or how you imagine that fitting it in, because beyond just Open Access journals or what they

call “gold APC” – there's other options as well and it might be helpful for students to be able to learn about what those actually are.

TOPS Moderator:

Thank you for sharing and [Speaker 4], do you think we are – as it is right now – do you think we are covering that in the lessons?

Speaker 4:

Yeah, a little bit. Do you have in **mind preprint things and open peer review** – that sort of thing?

Speaker 7:

Yeah, also there are some things that you can use when you're negotiating with the publisher to try and retain some of your rights over your article that I think would be helpful as well. And I would be happy to send them over. Those resources – if it would be helpful – and then also the green Open Access as they call it where **self-archiving** or **putting your manuscript in an open repository**, those kinds of opportunities as well I think would be important to cover.

Speaker 4:

We definitely talk about self-archiving. We do talk about preprints, and the specific piece that you mentioned about retaining rights over your work – that I'm not really sure we have a good handle on. So, if you have resources, definitely send them along, that would be helpful.

Speaker 7:

OK, great. Thank you.

TOPS Moderator:

OK, I have another question because I think we have only 10 minutes left and the question is: what is important to the topic but not critical for a beginner to learn? What do you think needs to be covered in this? It's not critical for beginners. Remember open core is supposed to be for someone that is not familiar with open core up to senior scientists, so we need to do think about the level of open core.

And as a reminder, in the chat, you can find the link for the GitHub in which have more details about this particular module.

Speaker 1:

Again, those might be in ethos [module], but in here or in ethos – is there a discussion or space for engagement around why people are resistant to open science?

Speaker 4:

Yeah. That is definitely in [the] ethos [module] and it also is in open results in

terms of what are the advantages to and obstacles that people face, commonly. So “scooping” was one of the community feedback [items] that I know people wanted to put in — we hadn't actually discussed scooping yet. But given that community feedback, I think it's one of those things you're suggesting that is an important topic in terms of people's resistance. I think in the Venn diagram of ethos and open results, it's in there.

Speaker 1:

Cool.

Speaker 7:

To that point, I would also – this is (Name) – say that other barriers or why folks may not be immediately on board with open science [is] because they might be concerned about the **cost they have to pay to publish something openly**. So that is a barrier because of the current system. And I think it would be helpful to also talk about that as well.

Speaker 4:

Yeah, that's a great point. We do explicitly mention cost and right now the kind of messaging is preprint – Open Access preprints are a great way to [go] if you don't have the ability to publish Open Access. And then we also explicitly discuss waiver programs as an option as well. If there are other cost barriers that you foresee that wouldn't be incorporated in those things I just mentioned, definitely point them out to us as well.

Speaker 7:

OK. Thank you.

TOPS Moderator:

OK, we are wrapping up soon. I want to go over another question which is: [reading from the Jamboard] from your experience, what practical or hands-on experience should a beginner gain from this module?

Yes, I see in the chat a plus one for non-English speakers. That is our plan as we evolve open core. Remember, this is the beginning of something really big. We hope this is going to evolve. Open core is just the beginning and we are planning to add more languages as we grow. For example, the solicitation that is coming out – one of the requirements inside that solicitation is that we are asking the community to produce training materials in different languages.

And we received the warning that this breakout room will close in two minutes, so I'm going to wrap up.

Speaker 4:

Can I ask a quick clarifying question for [Speaker 3]? Did you mean specifically in the modules, not necessarily how the modules are getting designed, but content

talking about within the context of open results, what resources are there for translation?

Speaker 3:

Yes, for authors that are publishing. I did not mean about these modules. I see [Speaker 7] has their hand up too.

TOPS Moderator:

Oh yes, [Speaker 7], go ahead.

Speaker 7:

So sorry, I just didn't put it down. This is me learning Teams as well.

TOPS Moderator:

We are all learning together. OK, just to wrap up before they kick us off. I want to ask again, what are we missing? What do you think we're missing in this module as we have it right now?

And remember, this is just breaking the ice with the community. This is the open call that we have to engage with the community.

###

END OF TRANSCRIPT

BEGINNING OF CHAT TEXT

1:31 PM [Speaker 2]

For reference https://github.com/nasa/Transform-to-Open-Science/blob/main/docs/Area2_Capacity_Sharing/OpenCore/open_results_module.md

1:33 PM [Speaker 1]

https://github.com/nasa/Transform-to-Open-Science/blob/main/docs/Area2_Capacity_Sharing/OpenCore/open_results_module.md

1:34 PM [Speaker 2]

And these are currently open issues/discussions around Open Results [Issues · learnopenscience/TOPS-Modules-Objectives-Outlines \(github.com\)](https://github.com/nasa/Transform-to-Open-Science/blob/main/docs/Area2_Capacity_Sharing/OpenCore/open_results_module.md)

1:34 PM [Speaker 1]

How is TOPS defining “results”? (Separate to data or paper conclusions)
https://github.com/nasa/Transform-to-Open-Science/blob/main/docs/Area2_Capacity_Sharing/OpenCore/open_results_module.md

1:36 PM [Speaker 2]

Overview - We will provide an overview of the research lifecycle and research outputs (Lesson 1). We will discuss the different stages of the research process, from planning all the way through (and beyond) dissemination. Along the way we will consider what the results of your work are, the “objects” in a research study, and how they can be shared (Lessons 2-3). By the end of the module, we will have looked at the important concepts and practices for publishing and sharing of research components before, during and after the project. Special attention will be given to ensuring ethical contributorship (i.e., making sure collaboration is fair, inclusive, and that credit is assigned transparently and equitably).

1:45 PM [Speaker 1]

"Impact" also lines up nicely with what NSF always wants in proposals

1:46 PM [Speaker 6]

Impact is a trailing indicator - data suggests open results have higher impact, but causality is hard to establish

1:50 PM [Speaker 1]

+1 great point about giving authors info on what they legally have the power to share

1:51 PM [Speaker 3]

If a primer on intellectual property (intelligible to academics) isn't in another module, maybe it would be useful here?

1:52 PM [Speaker 7]

Agree with [Speaker 3]

1:54 PM [Speaker 3]

What about resources for translation? (Either for non-English speakers, or for creating multi-lingual pubs).

1:54 PM [Speaker 1]

Also a huge barrier to 'developing world' researchers is historical injustices (where global north has stolen data & research) - massive amount of distrust

1:55 PM [Speaker 1]

+1 for non-English speaker tooling

1:57 PM [Speaker 5]

Is there any language on the value of reusability of Open Results, and what are supporting the impact assessment of those results?

END OF CHAT TEXT

JAMBOARD NOTES (Slide #5)

1. What is important to cover in this lesson?
 - Describe “results” that are not covered by “tools”, “software”, or “data” modules. Presumably contributions to the literature, but anything else?
 - Mitigating the risk of being “scooped”. Publish everything on a blog with timestamps.
 - Tools for non-English partners
2. Any proposed changes to the structure?
3. What practical or hands-on experience should a beginner gain from this module?
4. What is important to the topic, but not critical for a beginner to learn?